

Social Activism in the Writings of Mahasweta Devi and Arundhati Roy

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 1

Month : March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-2645

Impact Factor: 4.110

Citation:

Jansi, A. M. "Social Activism in the Writings of Mahasweta Devi and Arundhati Roy." *Shanlax International Journal of English*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 1–5.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2588174>

Dr. A M Jansi

*Assistant Professor of English
Gonzaga College of Arts and Science for Women
Kathampallam Krishnagiri, Tamil Nadu, India*

Abstract

Mahasweta Devi and Arundhati Roy are the well-known Indian women writers of post-colonial era. They are not only the fiction writers but also development critics as well as social activist writers. They have represented the marginalized section of the society in their writings. These two writers have been living their lives with the oppressed class to understand their problems and feel their difficulties and fight for the fundamental rights of the oppressed community through their writings and social movements. The present research paper attempts to explore the social activism of the two activist writers- Mahasweta Devi, a Bengali writer whose works are translated in English and Arundhati Roy, a writer in English, in her works of fiction and non-fiction. In their the documentation of exploitation of the suppressed classes, the writers have felt that it is high time that the exploited people rebel against the exploiting sections of the society. So this study is intended to throw light on their valuable and practically helpful contribution to Indian Literature and society as well.

Keywords : Mahasweta Devi, Arundhati Roy, Social Activism, Fiction, Non-fiction

Introduction

India is a complex and diverse land in terms of religion, class and the so-called caste system. Its official name is Republic of India, where democracy was installed after its independence from the British Empire. The Indian National Movement, where prominent personalities such as Mahatma Gandhi and Jawaharlal Nehru worked together to establish the basis of its future democracy. This was vital to the Indian Independence Act of 1947 that detached the country from Great Britain.

India's Constitution was written in 1949 and meant the end of colonialism in the subcontinent, even though India remained a member of the Commonwealth and many British laws and customs were adopted. During this period, the Hindu Code Bill was passed, which included the Hindu Marriage Act, the Hindu Succession Act, the Hindu Minority and Guardianship Act and the Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act. The Hindu Code Bill is still very relevant today, as it "covered legal issues pertaining to Hindu family law" (Majumbar 2007: 224). All this was meant to improve Indians'

social and economic circumstances and, therefore, to make their lives fairer. The most distinctive feature in India is its ancestral caste system, which is the form of stratification or hierarchy that was installed in India thousands of years ago and still remains in the country as its unbreakable social pyramid.

Mahasweta Devi comes from an activist family. Her father Manish Ghatak was a writer who wrote about Calcutta slums and her mother was a writer and social activist too. She belonged to an affluent middle class Bengali family with secular mindset. So the sense of social consciousness was already imbibed in her at a very young age mostly choose marginalized to develop her writings. In her works, most characters belong to Dalit and tribal groups and, therefore, are considered as subaltern and untouchables. Although their tribal origin is already enough tragedy, their stories, which usually involve the acts of men from higher classes, make them become outcasts even inside their own oppressed groups. In other words, Devi speaks “about the marginalized within the communities of the marginalized” (Chattopadhyay 2008: 211). This is where her originality resides: she is able not only to criticize the injustice inside the caste system, but to portray the cruelty between members of the same community, who contribute to enlarge the damage rather than prevent it.

Arundhati Roy was born in Shillong, to a Keralite Syrian Christian mother, the women’s rights activist Mary Roy and a Bengali father, Ranjithroy, a tea planter by profession. She spent her childhood in Ayamanam in Kerala and in her career, she worked for television and movies and also wrote screenplays, appeared as a performer also. She has written her first novel ‘God of Small Things’ which is semi-autobiographical and a major part of this novel captures her childhood experiences in Aymanam. Various themes that can be found in the novel are Indian history and politics. In addition to these, Roy evaluates the class relations and cultural tensions. Forbidden love becomes one of the integral themes of the novel. Not only this ‘love’ in its different forms becomes the basic theme of the novel, social discrimination and betrayal at different levels also are the important concerns of Roy in the novel. After her novel, Roy has devoted herself mainly to non-fiction and politics. She has got published her collection of essays and also has been working for social causes. She is a spokesperson of anti-globalisation. She criticizes strongly the approach of industrialisation and rapid development as currently being practiced in India.

The comparative study of Mahasweta Devi and Arundhati Roy is a daunting task owing to the vastness and variety of the literary realms that both the author embraces. Both Mahasweta Devi and Arundhati Roy’s writings and social activism have touched and inspired the lives of common people especially the dreg of the society and brought about collective consciousness to the elite as well as to the government. What both authors have in common though is their intention to demand social justice.

Gayatri Chakravarty Spivak, who has translated two collections of Devi’s stories including those in *Imaginary Maps*(1995) into English, suggest that these interplay of activism and literary writing in Devi’ s fiction can be of substantial interest to current academic discourse and practices. Spivak insists that Devi’s works suggest a model in which activism and writing can reflect upon each other, providing necessary visions of international and the possibilities of constructing a new kind of responsibility.

Roy in *The God of Small Things* depicts and critiques social and political structures through her deft characterization; the system of the gendered oppression and problematizes the association between feminists, liberalists, ideologists and activism and the ideas of ‘modernity’. She also depicts and emphasizes the Marxist political situation in India in general and Kerala in particular. Her creativity finds expression in her weaving of the autobiographical elements with social and political realities in India.

One important theme in the works of Mahasweta Devi is the positions of the tribals and the marginalized communities within India. She is a long time champion for the political, socio and economic advancement of these communities whom she characterizes as “suffering spectators of the India that is travelling towards the twenty first century”? These concerns can be seen in her works such as *Aranyer Adhikar* (1977), *Dust on the Road* (1997) *Chotti Munda* (1980) ‘*Tar Tir*’ (1980), *Bitter Soil* (1998) *Breast Stories* (1997), *Mother of 1084* (1997), *Baith-Four Stories* (2005), *Imaginary Maps* (1993). In all these works Mahasweta Devi reveals a sensitive conscience towards the society she lives in.

In her work-”*Stanadaini*” (The breast Giver) Devi brings to light the given realities of the amount of exploitation on women in the Indian society. The victim who takes up the job of breast feeding of a rich and spoiled Halder family is Yashoda. She dutifully breastfeed her own children, and the whole brood of Halder family. The Halders made this arrangement to keep their wives healthy and beautiful and also to keep the Halder man from going in immoral ways. Yasodha had to go through immense suffering in the process. As breastfeeding is subjected to biological demands - she has to conceive babies to feed more babies. So is the reason for the torturous routine of breeding children annually to keep her job going. The status of mother as divine with the virtue of dignity and service is indicated as the reader is made to believe. So she is taken as a mother capable of nurturing her children, an honourable job for womanhood. But Mahasweta breaks this accepted notion through the exploited Jasodha who is forgotten and left by her own children to die as she suffers from breast cancer. This brings into play the meaning of ‘mother India’ as a woman who is put to an acid test. It is in India where only few are favoured to enjoy all that is there and not because it is secular or giver of justice. So it is only a constituted framework before the world. So the idea of India stands vulnerable.

Mahasweta Devi herself says, “I am a woman, and I am writing but I am not writing of women alone. What I am writing is about class exploitation” which certainly mean exploitation at all levels. She depicts the unrevealed realities of India especially the deprived class of people. In her preface to *Agnigarbha* (1978) (womb of Fire) Mahasweta Devi says that rural India resembles a crematorium ground. She depicts the Indian villages where the landlords, the petty officers and the upper caste community who plays the dirty role in consuming most of the developmental fund and aids that comes from the center. In her work ‘*Draupadi*’, the naxalites and the deprived tribals unite to fight against the land owners and their goons, the police and the army. The story is about *Draupadi* or *Dopdi*’s heroic naxalite career. She manages to give a major blow to the army and the landlords. At last she is captured by the police when someone from the group informs her whereabouts. She is then taken into police custody and deprived of all her dignity as she is raped and her sex mutilated beyond recognition. In spite of this inhuman torture, she picks up her courage stands before her captor and brushes the officer with her naked breast and rings out in peel of laughter. This shocking scene stuns the police officer who is perplexed and breaks down only to realize the atrocities committed by the landlords, the police like himself, the army and the state. Through this story Mahasweta expose the hypocrisy of the Indian society and tears down the garb of the nation- state which wears a secular face.

In similar vein, Mahasweta deals with a moving story in the wake of the naxalite movement in India in her work- *Hajar Chaurasir Ma* (Mother of 1084) which is translated by Samik Bandyopadhyaya. The story revolves around *Sujata*, an anguished mother whose son *Bharati* a naxalite supporter is killed in an encounter supported by police, goondas and political parties. Since *Bharati*’s death, *Sujata* was always in search of the truth behind his death. She finally manages to unearth some of these truths on his birth and death anniversary which falls on the same day.

After his death, to avoid social embarrassment, her husband and the whole family hushed up the incident by bribing the police to erase Bharati out of the family name. So the deceased body of Bharati had no name on it but Corpse No-I084. The brutal killing of Bharati leaves the mother with many unanswered questions.

For instance, there is the question of young men and women losing faith in the Indian System which is as equal to losing faith in India. So these restless youths try to find meaning in joining the rebellious forces who want to bring about changes. They take up the painful, unpleasant and the rough road with the hope of positive changes rather than embracing the comfort of material richness and security of easy life at home. Mahasweta reveals that such rebellions are wiped out time and again but they refuse to die and resurrect like the story of the phoenix. These are people who have kept their conscience above the frills and frivolities of the privileged class of the society. Sujata's private emotion is the depiction of many Indian mothers who may have gone through such agonies of having lost their loved one in the Naxalite movement. It is not merely the question and problems of the tribals but a whole lot of questions on the various injustices done to the lower and unprivileged class in the society. It is a question of even the ordinary common people of India like the farmer, teachers, doctors, engineers who suffer under the atrocities of the political pressures and join hands with the rebels to find meaning in their existence a normal reaction of the conscience. So Mahasweta Devi's activism and writing do stir the conscience of every mindful Indian and compels one to see the reality around with open eyes.

Arundhati Roy's attitude towards the Naxalite movement is also in many ways similar to that of Mahasweta Devi. Roy seems to have a soft corner for the Naxalites and their cause for struggle. In fact she has been accused of publicly supporting the outlawed organization which is a violation of any responsible citizen. But she went ahead and made a personal journey to the jungle from where the Maoists lived and operated against the government. She wanted to have a firsthand knowledge of the Maoist organization and find out why they do what they do. (Naxalism) After her sojourn in the forbidden jungles of Chhattisgarh where even the most sophisticated machine guns of the state and the central government combined fear to penetrate, Roy wrote an essay titled 'Walking with the Comrade' published in the Outlook which talk about her experience with the Maoists. She tries to depict the real picture behind the jungle warfare between the government and the Maoists. She did not mind the volley of scathing criticism, accusation from the government, the police, the electronic media and her own contemporaries.

Roy also echoes similar concerns for the thousands of people displaced by the Narmada Dam building project. The cultivable land and their houses are destroyed due to the flood caused by the dam waters. So to sustain their existence these labourers flock to the cities and towns in search of jobs. Being alien to the new environment and the adjustment, they go through all sorts of jobs that are available to them at a very low wage. In the cities like Delhi, the labourers are made to live in the streets and makeshift tents in dreaded conditions. As Roy points out that they are treated like some unacknowledged citizens in their own countries.

Reading of her texts show that Mahasweta Devi also protests against the extraction of rich minerals inside the forest of tribal areas in the name of development. She says that the tribal forest have become the business ground for the rich, industrialists, contractors and politicians. We can see this attitude in an answer to a question by Anosh Malekar, whether her appealing and writing alone will make any change as people have become cynical these days. Mahasweta replied:

Look at me. I have never felt cynical. I will write, I will approach, and I will appeal to the people. We have to look for solutions. This country needs sensible solutions. Anyone born and brought up in India, having benefit from education and leading a decent life, cannot afford to be cynical. We are Indians.

Arundhati Roy also follows Mahasweta Devi and has similar views. *Algebra of Justice* is full of such scathing attack on Indian government policies, dam building projects, nuclear policy, war on terror and corporatization and privatization of market which she calls the Big Programmes in the name of development and security of the country.

In the early stages of their career, Devi and Roy wrote basically for their living but their literary journey did not remain restricted there. They continued to indulge in creative writing and research on the life around them. So Mahasweta Devi and Arundhati Roy complement each other in many ways; their forte is writing and activism. Both these authors deal with problems and issues of universal appeal like questions of equality, justice, dignity and love for humanity. Their activism and experience emit out through their writings. They use their pen as a sword to slash through the thickness of social injustice, inhuman brutalities and deprivation in many parts of India and in the world. Thus Roy has taken the footsteps of Mahasweta Devi which is a blend of writing and activism.

References

1. Devi, Mahasweta, *Chotti Munda and His Arrow*, Trans. Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak, Calcutta: Seagull Books, 2002.
2. Devi, Mahasweta, *Mother Of 1084*, Trans. Samik Bandyopadhyay, Calcutta: Seagull Books, 2008.
3. Roy, Arundhati, *The God Of Small Things*, New Delhi: Penguin Books, 1997.
4. Arundhati Roy, "The Colonization of Knowledge", *The Shape of the Beast in conversation with David Brasman*, 2001. (New Delhi: Penguin Viking, 2008) p.31. Print
5. Mahasweta Devi, *Imaginary Maps* (Translated by Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak) (Calcutta:Thema, 1995) p.IV. Print
6. Devi, Mahasweta, *Dust On The Road: The Activist writings of Mahasweta Devi*, Maitreya Ghatak(ed), Calcutta: Seagull Books, 2000.
7. Roy, Arundhati, 'The Greater Common Good', *The Algebra of Infinite Justice*, New Delhi: Penguin Books, pp. 47-141, 2001.
8. *Conversations with Arundhati Roy: The Shape of the Beast*, New Delhi: Penguin Books, 2009.
9. en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Arundhati_Roy
10. en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mahasweta_Devi